

STYLISTIC DEVICES IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract. This article demonstrates features of stylistic devices, the difficulties of their translation and some suggested ways of dealing them. Moreover, it indicates the importance of style and the ways of identifying stylistic devices.

Key words. Stylistic devices, onomatopoeia, alliteration, metaphor

СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИЕМЫ В ПЕРЕВОДЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются стилистические приемы и трудности их перевода, методы и подходы к их преодолению. В переводе подчеркивается важность стиля и умение идентифицировать стилистические приемы.

Ключевые слова. Стилистические приемы, аллитерация, метафора, ономотопея.

INTRODUCTION

Translation is an activity that is growing rapidly at the present time in the world. The studies of translation have also become hugely developed so far. However, it is not always easy to choose the right option for rendering the meaning of works for translators, as languages have their own national features of stylistic systems and they carry the imagery of the work. While giving the translation it is problematic to preserve original image of the text. Style plays an important role in the act of translation. Stylistic devices along with rhetorical devices are commonly used in literacy and writing to capture the attention of the readers by making the piece of writing remembered and to be hit the mark. Literary works are perceived when novelists and poets use stylistic devices to give a nudge to human senses. With the help of stylistic devices readers can differentiate a writer's writing style. Stylistic devices are included in expressive means of a language and they have a potential to make something uttered emphatic and expressive. In literary translation it is required to give precise result of rendering contents as well as to give certain conveyance of stylistic features of a work.

MAIN PART

Different languages have the same stylistic devices in core, but it defers in their function. Stylistic devices are commonly used in poetry, acting a role of intensifiers of mood and feeling in a poem. According to some notions taken from Galperin's work, stylistic devices are applied to give two meanings, the first one is ordinary meaning or is also called lexical and structural meaning, whereas the second is used to give special meaning. In his work, Galperin distinguishes expressive means with stylistic devices. Stylistic devices have a less degree of predictability than expressive means. In order to be interpreted easily, stylistic devices should be well known to the reader as a special code. Stylistic device can be used as a rhetorical device if it's used to convince, and as a literary device if it's used to express something. Before starting translation, it is crucial to identify the meaning of stylistic devices in a language which is to be translated into another language.¹

¹ English Stylistics. I.R.Galperin Page 136

Examples of stylistic devices:

Onomatopoeia – is a word which has sound of imitation of an object or an action which it describes. Onomatopoeic words are mostly used to add excitement and interest to the written work as well as humour to make the readers laugh. With onomatopoeia the work turns to be more fun and expressive. Some examples of onomatopoeic words are ‘meow’, ‘baa’, ‘hiss’, ‘neigh’, and ‘oink’ in English. In Uzbek we can encounter ‘myau’, ‘vov-vov’, ‘ma’, ‘taq-taq’, ‘paq-paq’ as onomatopoeic words. An important feature of translating onomatopoeia is that it should be adapted to the culture in the target language. Onomatopoeia is closely connected with the culture of the given language. Onomatopoeic words are mostly used in informal communication. Here are some examples of translated onomatopoeic words:

We could hear every *tick tock* of the clock, but the hours seemed never to pass.

Biz soat *chiq-chiqini* eshita oldik, ammo vaqt o'tganini sezmadik.

The dog *barked* all night.

It tuni bilan *vovulladi*.

The corn went *pop* in the microwave.

Jo'xori mikroto'lqinli pechda *paqillarda*.

Alliteration is one of the commonly encountered stylistic devices, which is the repetition of the same initial consonant sounds in each neighboring words of a sentence. Alliteration is used in literary works to grab the readers' attention. By using this style writer creates the mood. Alliteration, being a stylistic device, is commonly used mostly in children's writing and in poems. In a sentence or in a phrase there are words which start with the same sound and this sound is used repeatedly, creating alliteration. An Italian humanist Giovanni Pontano firstly used the term alliteration in his dialogue, explaining it as the same initial sound of words in a sentence. The aim of its usage is to make the phrase or rhythm catchy by adding emphasis. Especially in poetry, alliteration creates musicality, mood and humor. In translation translators are not always able to keep the alliteration, due to the different vocabulary stock of languages.

For example: 'Betty Botter bought some butter, but she said, this butter's bitter; if I put it in my batter, it will make my batter bitter, but a bit of better butter will make my batter better.'²

Betti Botter saryog' sotib oldi, aytishicha saryog' achchiq; agar saryog'ni quymoq qorishmasiga solsam, quymoq qorishmasini achchiqlashtiradi, lekin sal yaxshiroq saryog' solsam yaxshilaydi.

Metaphor. Metaphor is a stylistic device used to compare two things which are characterized by different expressions sharing the same qualities. The translation of metaphors is highly dependent to the culture. A metaphor that is widely understood in one language might not have the same impact or make sense when directly translated into another language with different cultural references. Metaphors often derive their significance from the particular context in which they are employed. Translating a metaphor without considering its contextual importance can result in a loss of richness and intricacy in the original meaning. Metaphors frequently incorporate creative wordplay and imaginative connections that can be challenging to reproduce in another language without losing their original impact.

² The Jingle Book (1899) Page 86

CONCLUSION

When translating a metaphor to a new context, a translator can choose from three options: using an exact equivalent of the original metaphor, finding a different metaphor that conveys a similar meaning, or replacing the untranslatable metaphor with a literal paraphrase. Examples:

Time is money. (Vaqt puldir.)

She is an apple of my eye. (U ko'zimning qorachig'i.)

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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